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Video games as a tool for learning English vocabulary for young learners

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Annotation. The aim of this paper is to highlight that games are effective tools when devised to explain vocabularies and they make it easier to remember their meanings. This paper deals with a literature review of teaching English vocabulary to young learners using games. Then it discusses the importance of using games in teaching vocabulary and in what way using them is helpful.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolaning maqsadi o'yinlar lug'atlarni tushuntirish uchun samarali vosita ekanligini va ular ma'nolarini eslab qolishni osonlashtirishini ta'kidlash. Ushbu maqola o'yinlardan foydalangan holda yosh o'quvchilarga ingliz tili lug'atini o'rgatish bo'yicha adabiyotlarni ko'rib chiqish bilan bog'liq. Keyin lug'atni o'rgatishda o'yinlardan foydalanishning ahamiyati va ulardan qanday foydalanish samarali ekanligi haqida so'z boradi.

Аннотация. Цель этой статьи состоит в том, чтобы подчеркнуть, что игры являются эффективными инструментами для объяснения словарного запаса и облегчают запоминание их значений. Эта статья посвящена обзору

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литературы по обучению английской лексике молодых учащихся с помощью игр. Затем обсуждается важность использования игр в обучении словарному запасу и их полезность.

Key words: *young learners, games, vocabulary, practical challenges, practical, implication.*

Kalitso‘zlar: *yosh o‘quvchilar, o‘yinlar, lug‘at, amaliy vazifalar, amaliy, imo-ishora*

Ключевые слова: *младшие школьники, игры, словарный запас, практические задачи, практические, значение*

Over the last few decades, teaching English has become a phenomenon in Uzbekistan, especially to young learners. English is taught as a main subject in kindergarten and elementary schools. Like any other children, Uzbeks accept new foreign languages easily, but they get bored very quickly if the teacher teaches them using the old conventional methods and techniques so the usage of new modern technological devises and video games as a part of a curriculum can make the learning process easier and more enjoyable. First, games bring in relaxation and fun for students, thus help them learn and retain new words more easily. Second, games usually involve friendly competition and they keep learners interested. These create the motivation for learners of English to get involved and participate actively in the learning activities.

Initially, the main idea of video games was playing in a virtual environment presented through two dimensional graphics that are primitive and outdated

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compared to the highly advanced games of recent years. The common stereotype among the people is that video games are made for “entertainment” only (Shaffer, Halverson, Squire, & Gee, 2005), although this may apply to “old school” video games, the case is entirely different nowadays with the embedment of different elements such as realistic imagery, compelling storylines, sophisticated gameplay systems, simulation of social interactivity and etc. These elements play their role in involving the gamer in learning and acquiring different sorts of knowledge at the same time in a semi- authentic context, and in a non- systematic way, promoting the autonomy of learning (Holec, 1981, as cited in Chik, 2014). One of the aspects of knowledge gained from video games is second language learning and acquisition, and this is the axis around which this research paper revolves.

Using video games to improve foreign language skills is a useful tool because the player sees words being used in context. This helps to improve vocabulary skills. At the same time, the player is seeing the objects of vocabulary during learning. This allows for the association of words with pictures. Repetition of words and concepts is the way in which we embed our vocabulary. As you’re playing a video game, you’ll be hearing the same words over and over, associating words with objects and learning without even realising that you’re doing so, and the more you play the game, the more entrenched those memories and associations become.

Finding the right learning platform couldn’t be easier. There are multiple platforms on which people interested in learning a new language can play. PlayStation, Xbox, Nintendo, Windows for PC, Smartphones etc. And all you need

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do is select the target language you wish to learn and you're ready to go. Multiplayer Video Games have also been so popular nowadays, as you communicate with other players in English, you can improve your skills with the language. Multiplayer video games will give you an opportunity to communicate with your friends in English. This can be a phrase, a word, or anything. Whatever you learn from these games is an added benefit. Accordingly, games help students to retain unfamiliar vocabulary, to associate new information with their surroundings and to develop their language and communicative skills.

Regardless of their genre, video games have the potential to contribute positively to the language learning process. For example, playing computer games enhances the students' cognitive skills (Gnambs & Appel, 2016). Additionally, some studies show playing educational computer games in language learning has positive effects on learners. For instance, vocabulary learning in students who play games is higher than the ones who are subjected to traditional teaching methods such as directing students to learn through memorization and recitation techniques (AlShaiji, 2015; Ashraf et al., 2014; Smith et al., 2013; Yip & Kwan, 2006). Besides, these games provide higher retention rates of vocabulary than the traditional teaching methods (Aghlara & Tamjid, 2011; Franciosi et al., 2016; Smith et al., 2013). Borgonovi (2016) found in his research covering 26 countries that computer games also had positive effects on reading skills. Cornillie et al. (2012) emphasized that computer games providing feedback for students keep them highly motivated, which makes it quite promising to use these games in language teaching. Hung et al. (2018) reviewed the literature on the acquisition of

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educational games in

language learning. They identified six potential categories of language learning from the most frequently reported to the least: emotional/psychological states, language acquisition, participatory behaviors, correlational results, knowledge acquisition, and contemporary competencies.

It is undeniable that those video games have become an inseparable part of children and adults' leisure-time activities, and that they have become their virtual world where they find themselves taking the roles of different identities and learning different skills (Shaffer, Halverson, Squire, & Gee, 2005). Individuals who play these games are in reality involved in a strenuous process to solve puzzles, defeat enemies, reach new levels and reach the game's end. It is a challenge between the player and the game itself. Gee (2005) alleges that learning by doing, in an entertaining fashion, is more effective than simply acquiring the facts without practicing them, and video games actually involve the gamer in practicing certain skills in order to reach new horizons in the game while the gamer's enjoyment is at its heights. In a semi-ethnographic study carried out by Steinkuehler (2010) on a young adult student known by his online nickname "Julio", it was found that Julio's digital reading literacy acquired from video games, and video game fan-based online sites was as high as that of advanced-level reading texts, and that Julio tends to lose interest and achieve lower marks in conventional advanced reading exams, because he is not involved in a computer game. Thorne, Black and Sykes (2014) posited that learning a second language in school is confined by the settings of the school itself, limiting the breadth of

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language use, and that online gaming with its online communities provide a greater opportunity to learn, acquire and practicing the second language.

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